

Research Article

Appraising Insecurity and Its Socio-Economic Consequences in Nigeria: A Study of Ondo State

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Abstract

The unprecedented spate of insecurity in recent times in Nigeria has ignited a lot of intellectual excursions that are centred on the contributory factors and panaceas to the unquantifiable consequences that the security challenges have placed on the nation. The government formulated policies and actions at all levels have not played pivotal roles to checkmate the rising criminal activities. Cato Institute-a Washington DC-based public policy research organisation rated Nigeria unsafe because of the escalations of crimes within and across the territory of the country. Thus, the study elicited primary data through a self-administered questionnaire from 300 respondents, which comprised civilians, military and Para-military officers within Ondo state, to investigate insecurity and its socio-economic consequences using the Anomie theory of crime as a theoretical fulcrum. Secondary data were also gathered from relevant articles, newspapers, publications and textbooks to support the field experiment. After the analysis of data with the use of descriptive statistics, the study revealed that the rate of insecurity is high in Ondo state. It was further shown that youth unemployment, poverty, poor policing system, porosity of poorly demarcated borders, Ethno-religious crises, political leadership tussles, weak security, legal and legislative systems among other factors and conditions contribute significantly to the security quagmire in Ondo state. In the same vein, according to the study, some of the attendant consequences of insecurity include but not limited to discouragement of investments, destruction of residences and places of worship, internal displacement of persons, brain drain, migration, economic loss, social discomfort, and death of citizens. The study therefore, concluded that efforts of the governments at all levels have not been effective to checkmate the criminal activities. To stem the rising wave of insecurity, the study recommended more coordinated and pro-active socio-economic measures, community policing, strategic military operations, effective border monitoring, and good governance among others.

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ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Keywords: Insecurity, Community policing, borders, socio-economic consequences, criminal activities.

Received: 02 November 2024

Accepted: 28 January 2025

Citation: Akinola-Fajojuto, O. R. (2025). Appraising Insecurity and Its Socio-Economic Consequences in Nigeria: A Study of Ondo State. *Continental J. Applied Science*, 20(1), 39–60. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14805067

Introduction

Nigeria is one of the unsafe places to live on the planet according to CATO-Institute- A Washington DC-based Public Policy research organisation while it was ranked 6th on the Scale of Global Terrorism Index (GTI) in 2021. These various ratings have lent credence to the state of violence in the country. The escalation of crimes in recent times, has generated growing concern among governments, local and international observers and security stakeholders. Insecurity, according to Igbuzor (2011), is a state of being exposed to risk or anxiety. Emenari, Nwaezuoke and Adewale (2014) defined insecurity as a state of fear or anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of protection. According to Akingbade, Olabamiji and Ajala (2022), the nation is bedevilled with incessant ethnic religious crises with the debilitating challenges associated with Boko Haram insurgency in the Northeast.

The unprecedented level of security through past and recent political dispensations have prompted militia groups in the south, ritual killings in the east and west, kidnappings in the east and south, political and non-political calculated assassinations across the nations (Ndubuisi- Okolo and Anigbuogu (2019). According to Adagba, Ugwu and Eme (2012), unemployment and poverty among Nigerians especially the youths is a major cause of insecurity and violent crimes in Nigeria. The porous borders of Nigeria, however continues to support trans-border crimes and instability in region as a result of lack of appropriate mechanism to monitor movement and illegal activities across borders (Omoniyi, 2023). The porous borders allow unchecked inflow of small arms and light weapons into the country which has aided militancy and criminality in Nigeria.

Available statistics show that Nigeria has over eight million illegal weapons in West Africa. Nigerian porous frontiers have also witnessed influx of migrants from neighbouring countries such as republic of Niger, Chad and Republic of Benin who fuel criminal acts in Nigeria (Udeoba and Eze, 2021). Other conditions and factors contributing to insecurity quagmire in Nigeria have been identified by different scholars. These include ethnic/religions crises, weak security, loss of socio-cultural and communal

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ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

value system, inadequate funding of security agencies, ineffective inter-agency coordination and collaboration and political leadership tussles, among others.

Banditry, commercial kidnappings, arson, bombing of places of worship assassinations, organised armed robberies are daily occurrences in Nigeria and have caused negative implications on the economy and Nigeria national life. However, the security challenges in different parts of the country have refused to be curtailed by the underfunded, overstretched and undertrained security agents. They lack the capacity to discharge their core mandate of maintaining law and order, and protecting lives and property (Olubade and Ogunnoiki,2020).

In the same vein, the regional security outfits in Nigeria such as “Operation Amotekun” in the southwest, “Shege-Ka-Fasa” in the Northern Nigeria and “Operation Ogbuniwe” in the Eastern Nigeria have not actually contributed to the reduction of criminal incidences in all the six geo-political zones. Hence, there are growing calls for re-engineering of security architecture in order to produce a sustainable peaceful environment and development in Ondo state and Nigeria.

Problem Statement

The spate of insecurity in Nigeria ditto Ondo state has largely been attributed to the failure of the government to provide basic needs for its citizens particularly the young and active population despite the availability of human and natural resources. The resultant frustration by the inability of the masses to acquire necessities of life like shelter, food, education and clothing usually precipitate violence and criminal activities.

Some ugly situations such as corruption among the ruling elite have led to diversion of funds that are meant for job creation, industrialisation and provisions of infrastructure into their private accounts. The rate of youth unemployment in Ondo State is very high and the state has continued to witness' increased incidents of abductions of its citizens by kidnappers on the highways, and farmlands, ritual killings, bank robberies, cybercrimes, extremism, terrorist attacks and other crimes.

The creation of ‘Amotekun’ security outfit by Ondo State government on August 11, 2020, a move to confront the challenges of insecurity in the state has not yielded the desired results. This worrisome situation has prompted this study which aims to appraise the insecurity in the state with the purpose of recommending remedies.

Objectives of the Study

The general Objective of the study is to appraise the socio-economic consequences of insecurity in Ondo State.

Specific objectives, however, are to:

1. Ascertain the level of insecurity in Ondo State.
2. Access the causes of insecurity in Ondo State.
3. Examine the socio-economic consequences of insecurity in Ondo State.
4. Investigate the effectiveness of government's efforts in combating insecurity in Ondo State.

Research Questions

This study is guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the level of insecurity in Ondo State?
2. What are the causes of insecurity in Ondo State?
3. What are the socio-economic consequence of insecurity in Ondo State?
4. Are governments' efforts effective in combating insecurity in Ondo State?

Literature Review

Insecurity in Nigeria

Insecurity in Nigeria has become a critical issue of high concern locally and internationally. Nigeria with a population of over 250 million citizens is perceived to be the most populous black nation and a giant of Africa is bedevilled with unprecedented incidences of security challenges ranging from the activities of Fulani Herdsmen, terrorism/violent extremism, armed banditry, commercial kidnappings, piracy, smuggling, crude oil theft, successionist agitations, proliferation of arms and light weapons, cyber fraud, assassinations, arsons and other violent crimes.

These activities of criminals have resulted in the burning of places of worship, the bombing of marketplaces, police stations, schools, shops, army barracks, oil pipelines, and residential houses, and kidnapping of indigenes and foreign workers, and the death of thousands of victims.

These insecurity challenges have caused the Nigerian government to make huge allocations of its budget for the protection of lives and property at the detriment of resources that are meant for another developmental projects.

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ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Other symptoms of insecurity as evident in Nigeria include deterioration of economic, political, social, and religious values, and severe implications on industrialisation and sustainable development because insecure and unsafe environments are not only inimical to industrialisation but pose threat to local and foreign investment as no reasonable investors will be willing to expend his funds in violent or violence-prone communities (Akingboye, 2019, June 11), (Akingbade 2022).

Okonkwo, Ndubuisi-Okolo and Anigbuogu (2015) opined that the inability of government to provide a secure and conducive environment for protection of lives, properties and the conduct of business and numerous economic activities has led to lack of interest and dissatisfaction among business investors.

Therefore, ineptitude of the government, institutional failures and attitudes of public office holders towards the welfares of downtrodden masses have been fingered as major factors in exacerbating the state of insecurity in Nigeria.

Federal government's responses to insecurity in Nigeria

Nigeria is witnessing an unprecedented level of insecurity since the inception of the immediate past Administration till the present democratic political dispensation (Ndubuisi-Okolo and Anigbuogu, 2019). Consequently, to protect national values against the existing and potential adversaries. Nigeria complies with some conditions. There is also external collaboration at regional, continental and global levels to address Nigeria's security interest (Omoniyi, 2023). This interest covers all the strategic factors that affect the country's development including law and order, developmental efforts, political and social stability, trade and economic development and relations with other countries (Akonbede, 2013). To curb insecurity problems in Nigeria, the National Assembly has passed relevant laws to checkmate the new and emerging threats to a constitutional democracy. For examples, in the last ten (10) years, some of these laws are: Anti-terrorism Act, Anti-piracy Act and Extraction Act are among bold and articulated legislative steps to be taken by the government to make crimes unattractive (Omoniyi, 2023).

Militancy measures are the most visible efforts adopted by the Nigerian government in its fight terrorism especially Boko Haram sect in the North East. Procurement of military equipment and weapons, defence operations, procurement for upgrade of capacities and infrastructure and recruitment of military and Paramilitary personnel have gulped billions of naira of the defence budgets since 2003. The Armed forces and other security

agencies are currently conducting various operations in the Northern part of the country against banditry such as operations “Hadarin” and “Ex Sahel Sanity” while some state governments have engaged the armed bandits in reconciliatory efforts have led to unconditional release of scores kidnapped victims (Olubade and Ogunnoiki (2015), (Ozoigbo, 2019) and (Musa,2021).

Causes of insecurity in Nigeria

The magnitude of insecurity in Nigeria has been attributed to myriad of factors. Many of these contributory factors have been identified by many scholars and security experts. Insecurity challenges have retarded the nation’s socio-economic growth and development by stifling the smooth flow of business activities in the country. The following factors are principally responsible for the flourish of criminal activities in Nigeria.

Youth unemployment and widespread poverty:

Poverty and unemployment lead to economic disparity and depravity which fuels terrorism and criminality in Nigeria. The degree with which unemployed youths are roaming about the street is alarming. These jobless active young population employ themselves by engaging in illegal activities such as kidnapping, robbery, child abduction, cybercrimes, ritual killings, and other nefarious activities. According to Osarensen and Edomwonyi-Olu (2020) despite Nigerian huge resources and oil wealth, poverty is still rampant to the extent that the country is ranked one of the 20th poorest countries in the world. Over 70 percent of the population is classified poor, with 35 percent living in abject poverty. In Ondo State, the high level of unemployment and poverty among citizens especially the youths have attracted so many of them to violent crimes according to Oyinloye, Olamiju and Otokiti (2017).

Porous and poorly demarcated borders:

Nigeria is a country located on the western coast of the African continent. The country shares porous land and maritime boundaries with several countries like Benin Republic, Niger, Cameroon and Chad. Individual movements are largely undocumented and untracked. This unrestricted movements of goods and persons have contributed to proliferation of small arms and light weapons into the country contributing to the high degree of insecurity in Nigeria (Nwagboso, 2012). The security reports confirmed the existence of several bandits' camps in various locations scattered across the forest of the Southeast and Southwest. Incidentally, Ondo State one of the six southwest states shares boundaries with Kogi State of the North Central Nigeria, making the state more vulnerable to cross-border attacks.

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ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Poor policing system:

This results from inadequate law enforcement agents or man force to carry out effective policing and inadequate equipment for the security arm of government, both in weaponry and training. According to Ikenga and Efebeh (2013), the police population ratio in Nigeria is 1:450 which falls below the standard set by the United Nations. The implication of this is that Nigeria will not be properly policed resulting to inability of Nigerian police force to effectively and efficiently combat criminal activities in Nigeria.

Tussle for political power

The incessant rancour among political leaders within same party and rancour between the ruling party and opposition party often lead to escalated tensions, politically-related assassination, arson and destruction of property of perceived enemies during inter-play of powers by ambitious politicians or their sympathisers who will willingly encourage procurement of weapons in order to pursue their inordinate political ambitions (Igbuzor, 2011). In the last gubernatorial election in Ondo State in 2021, there were reported cases of attacks by people suspected to be members of ruling party who unleashed mayhem on the opposition party members during the electioneer campaigns at Owo and Oba Akoko. In Nigeria, divisions among numerous political parties have caused untimely death of many politicians.

Ethnic-religious crises

Ethnic/Religious conflict has been identified as a major source of insecurity in Nigeria. (Udeoba and Eze, 2021). Lack of cordiality, mistrust, fear of domination and oppression between members of one ethnic or religious group and another group in a pluralistic society have often led to violent confrontations and frequent clashes between dominant groups and religions in Nigeria.

Weak judicial system

Nigeria has a weak criminal justice system which contributes to the culture of impunity that breeds violence (Musa, 2021). The Nigeria law enforcement agencies have weak capacities to rigorously investigate cases in order to get justice. This has created loss of confidence of the citizens in the judiciary system which has made them, more often than not, to resort to self -help and jungle justice that normally exacerbates the cycle of violence.

Substances abuse

The abuse of drugs and other psychosocial substances are the major motivators for most domestic and violent crimes including extremism. In a paper presented by Rear Admiral

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ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Yaminu Ehinomen M. Musa, Coordinator, Counter Terrorism Centre, Office of the National Security Adviser, Presidency, Abuja-Nigeria, he states that the results obtained from samples from the cadaver of some detonated suicide bombers in the north eastern part of Nigeria indicated trace of such substances in the corpses, indicating that most of them were under the influence of the substances while carrying out the violent extremist acts. The long time and irresponsible use of chemicals, fertilizers and explosive items have caused proliferation of crimes.

Successionist agitations

The democratisation of countries, increased rights of freedom of associations, and advancement in information, communication and technology had consequently, covertly or overtly increased agitations and self -determination by groups within the country (Oyinloye, Olamiju and Otokiti, 2017). These groups such as Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) in the Eastern Nigeria, Pro Oduduwa Republic group in South-western Nigeria and the Islamic movement of Nigeria (IMN) in the Northern Nigeria have created activities that have raised security concerns in recent years. Most especially, the IPOB have taken arms against the state and continue to attack the security forces, government institutions, democratic infrastructure as well as law abiding citizens.

Insecurity in Ondo State

Ondo state is one of the 36 states of Nigeria that was carved out of the former Western on February 3, 1976 by the former military regime of Gen Yakubu Gowon. According to Wikipedia, Ondo State lies between latitudes 5⁰⁵1E and 7⁰¹⁰1N of the equator; and longitudes 4⁰²¹1E and 6⁰⁰⁵1E of the meridians. It is bound by Ekiti to the North, Kogi state to the Northeast, Edo State to the East, Delta state to the Southeast, Ogun state to the Southeast, Osun state to the Northwest and the Atlantic Ocean to the South. The state includes mangrove-swamp forest near the Bight of Benin, it was nicknamed the "Sunshine state". Ondo state is the 18th most populated state in Nigeria and the 25th largest state by landmass. The population of the state was put at 3,460,877 according to 2006 census comprising 18 local government areas.

Recently, Ondo state has witnessed escalations of criminal activities across its eighteen local government areas. The rate of reported fatalities has increased since 2015 which has given rise to concerns of both the residents and the governments. Kidnappings of commuters and notable personalities on the highways, and rural dwellers on their farmlands have become nightmarish occurrences. The following cases of the nefarious activities of criminals within the state as reported by Nigerian Newspapers revealed gory situations:

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- 1) Kidnapping of Chief Olu Falae, the former finance minister and Secretary to the Federal Military government at Ilu-Abo, Ondo state on the 21st September, 2015 by Fulani Herdsmen (Akinloye, 2016, April 10).
- 2) Killing of Mrs Funke Olakunrin, daughter of the Afenifere leader, Chief Reuben Fasonranti, along Ondo-Ore Road, Ondo State on 12th July, 2019 (Akinkuotu, 2019, July 19).
- 3) The killing of at least 40 church worshippers at a catholic church in the city of Owo, Ondo state. The massacre was suspected to be carried out by the Islamic State-West Africa Province (Peter, 2022, June 8).
- 4) Abduction of 25 members of the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC), Oke-Igan, Akure along Owo-Ifon on their way to a funeral ceremony on September 29, 2023 (Oluwole, 2023, September 30).
- 5) The killing of ex-lover by Bankole Oginni in Akure allegedly for money ritual purposes on August 6, 2023 (Gbadamosi, 2023, August 13).
- 6) Killing of Olufon of Ifon, Oba Adeusi Isreal along Ifon-Benin expressway Ondo state by suspected kidnappers on the 26th November, 2020 (Osinusi, 2020, November 7).
- 7) The killing of Olorunfemi Temitope, a suspected internet fraudster in Ijoka area by mob on April 9, 2023 (Dada, 2023, April 27).
- 8) Robbery attack of a branch of Union Bank in Ode-Irele town in Ondo state on November 25, 2020 (Dada, 2020, November 25).
- 9) Killing of three persons by a gang of arrived robbers at Ilara-Mokin town in Ifedore Local government area of Ondo state on Thursday, July 14, 2021 during an operation at a branch of the United Bank for Africa (Adejumo, 2021, July 15).

In a move to confront the challenges insecurity in Ondo State, the Amotekun corps officers of the Ondo State Security Network Agency were inaugurated on Tuesday, August 11, 2020 by the state government. This first autonomous regional security outfit was founded on 9th January, 2020 in Ibadan, Oyo State by six states of the Southwest Nigeria namely; Lagos, Oyo, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Ekiti States. Their operations are to assist police, security agents and traditional rulers in combating terrorism, banditry, armed robbery, kidnapping and also helps in settling herdsmen and farmers conflicts in the region.

Socio-Economic Consequences of Insecurity in Nigeria

Reduced industrialization drive:

Modern economic growth and development needs rapid industrialization. But there is enormous security challenge in Nigeria which has hampered the relentless efforts of government to industrialize the country since 1960's, after independence. According to Ozoigbo (2019), incessant attacks across the land has reduced the interests of local and foreign investors and some have been forced to relocate or closed down business because of the inability of the security agents to guarantee safety and national security in the country. To say at least, many factories have been burnt down, lives and properties had been lost. These untoward happenings affect industrial growth and development in Nigeria.

Food scarcity

Insecurity in Nigeria is having monumental negative effects on farming activities with attendant tolls on food availability. Agricultural activities have been disrupted due to the incessant attacks by Boko Haram and nefarious activities of bandits and herdsmen farmer crises particularly in the North Eastern and North Central part of Nigeria.

Unemployment

High incidences of insecurity in Nigeria have destroyed infrastructure, private and government owned establishments. This has made investments to be unattractive to investors. The periods of violence will stop business operations or outright closure of many companies especially in the areas that commonly witness occurrences of violence. In the same vein, disruption of agricultural practices by the criminal herdsmen whose have held the southwest, south-south, south-east to ransom have discouraged engagement of local farmers in farming.

Economic consequences

Creation of wealth for economic development is one of the cardinal objectives of any government. To achieve this, there should be vibrant economic activities which can be guaranteed by secure and safe environment, Peaceful co-existence of the citizens provides unhindered business endeavours. The huge cost of security challenges in terms of obvious destruction of private and public property in Ondo state and Nigeria are huge.

Disruption of academic programmes

The increase pace of insecurity in the country has significantly threatened education in the country. Today, Nigeria has one of the world's highest numbers of out-of-school children (13.2 million according to the United Nations Children Fund (UNICEF) which

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is attributed to kidnapping of students from school by Islamic extremists (Ikenga and Efebeh 2013). This discourages school enrolment and continuity of academic stay. For instance, between December 2020-June 2021 over 1,000 students and staff have been kidnapped in 9 school abductions reported in North West Zone.

Migration

Destruction of infrastructure, villages and farmlands by terrorists and harmed bandits as well as kinetic engagements of security forces have created social dislocations and discomfort. This has in turn led to an increase in migration of people from the North eastern parts of the country and other high threat areas along the borders. However, Achumba, Ighomereho and Akpor-Robamo (2013) observed that high level of insecurity in a particular area or region will lead to migration of people which could result to shortage of skilled manpower.

Increase in internally displaced persons (IDPS)

According to Musa (2020), increased violence and forced displacement continue to affect the humanitarian situation in Nigeria. This steady increase of displaced persons is being orchestrated by conflicts across Nigeria. From available data, over 2.4million people are estimated to have been displaced from their families and communities. This crisis have put stress on the existing system of the host communities in terms of demand for food, shelters, water, healthcare and other public services.

Theoretical Framework

Anomie theory of crime

For over a century, Anomie Theory had a profound impact on the direction of sociological criminology. Originally, emerging in classical social thoughts as an analytical tool to study how broadly defined social conditions influence normative regulation and rates of deviant behaviour. Anomie was introduced as an analytical tool for studying the social causes of deviance in the writings of the French sociologist, Emile Durkheim in 1897, in his book suicide, Emile Durkheim used Anomie to refer to the lack of integration or social cohesion within a society. The discrepancy between goals of the people and the available means to achieve them most times motivate deviance.

In the same development, a sense of alienation and hopelessness in a society or group is often a response to societal upheaval. This causes the breakdown of an individual's usual social and ethical standards. Durkheim also posted that, when social institutions such as family, education and work lose control over people, they deprive these people of

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socialization. A state called Anomie results which can lead to criminal and deviant behaviour.

The import of this theory is that Nigeria is riddled with evident rejection of shared values and norms of behaviour. The people become too focused on acquiring wealth and possessions, they lose sight of what is important in life. This leads to feelings of emptiness and dissatisfaction, even if they have everything they could ever want. Also, perennial upheavals such as wars or natural disaster in Nigeria lead to lack of relevance of traditional institutions and values, people who feel lost and confused can engaged in some actions which are outside the norms of the society like religious extremism, looting, arson and vandalization. The religious extremism is an example of self-righteousness which leads to Anomie. Many self -righteous individuals are those who believe that are morally superior to others and have the right to force their beliefs on others as the cases of Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria.

Methodology

The study aims to appraise the insecurity and its socio-economic consequences in Nigeria, referencing Ondo State. A purposive sampling design was used where 300 respondents which comprised 235 civilians, 35 military and 30 Para-military personnel who were selected across the eighteen Local Government Areas of the state through multi-stage sampling technique. Information was obtained from the participants with the aid of self-structured questionnaire. Their responses were coded and treated with confidentiality, the questionnaire consists of 21 variables designed to elicit information on socio-demographic profile of the participants and on the rate, causes, socio-economic consequences and effectiveness of government efforts in combating the crimes of insecurity in Nigeria using Ondo state as a study.

The analytical tools involved the use of numbers, frequency tables and percentages.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S/N	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Male	203	67.67
	Female	97	32.33
	Total	300	100
2	Age		
	25-34	32	10.67
	35-44	107	35.67
	45-54	68	22.67
	55-64	81	27
	65-74	12	4
	TOTAL	300	100
3	Education		
	Secondary School and above	248	82.67
	No formal Education	52	17.33
	Total	300	100
3	Education		
4	Profession		
	Civilians	235	78.33
	Law Enforcement Agents	65	21.67
	Total	300	100

Source: Field Report 2023

Table 1 presents Socio-Demographic profile of the respondents. From the analysis, the table shows out of the 300 respondents, 203(67.67%) are male while 97(32.33%) are female. Also, 32(10.67%) respondents fall within the age bracket of 25-34 years; 107(35.67%) are within 35-44 years; 68(22.67%) are within 45-54 years; 81(27%) are within 55-64 years; while 12(4%) respondents are within 65-74 years of age.

The table further revealed 248(82.67%) respondents attended at least secondary school while 52(17.33%) have no formal education. In the same vein, 235 respondents

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representing 78.33% are civilians comprising of residents at the borders, civil servants, traditional rulers, community heads, religious leaders, artisans, youth representatives and business men and women; 65 (21.67%) are law enforcement officers of Nigerian Army, Police force, Prison services, Nigeria Defence and Security Services, and Amotekun Security Network.

Research Question 1: What is the rate of insecurity in Ondo State?

Table 2: The Respondents' opinions on the rate of insecurity in Ondo State

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
High	193	64.33%
Medium	71	23.67%
Low	36	12%
Total	300	100

Source: Field report 2023

Table 2 presents the respondents' opinions on the rate of insecurity in Ondo State. The table revealed that out of the 300 respondents, 193 (64.33%) respondents opined that the rate of insecurity is high in Ondo State; 71(23.67%) agreed that the rate of insecurity is medium while 36 (12%) agreed that the rate of insecurity is low in the State. From the analysis above, it can be inferred that the majority of the respondents are of the opinion that the rate of insecurity is high in Ondo State based on the reported cases of criminal activities and the high records of pre-disposing factors such as youth unemployment and poverty.

Research Question 2: What are the major causes of insecurity in Ondo State?

Table 3: Respondents opinions on the major causes of insecurity in Ondo State.

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Unemployment/Poverty	97	32.33
2	Porous Borders	59	19.67
3	Poor Community Policing	32	10.67
4	Political Activities	25	8.33
5	Weak Judicial System	31	10.33
6	Ethno-Religious Conflicts	22	7.33
7	Drug Substances Abuse	15	5
8	ICT advancement	19	6.33
TOTAL		300	100

Source: Field report 2023

Table 3 presents the opinions of the respondents on the major causes of insecurity in Ondo State. The table shows that out of 300 respondents, 97(32.33%) respondents agreed that unemployment/poverty is the major cause of insecurity in Ondo State; 59(19.67%) agreed with porous borders; 32(10.67%) agreed with poor community policing; 31(10.33%) agreed with weak judicial system; 25(8.33%) agreed with political activities; 22(7.33%) agreed with ethno-religious conflicts; 15(5%) agreed with drug/substances abuse while 19(6.33%) agreed with Information Communication and Technology (ICT) advancement as the major causes of insecurity in Ondo State. From the analysis above, it can be interred that majority of the respondents agreed that unemployment/poverty is the major cause of insecurity in Ondo State.

Research Question 3: What are the socio-economic consequences of insecurity in Ondo State?

Table 4: Respondents' opinions on the socio-economic consequences of insecurity in Ondo State.

S/N	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Poor Industrial Growth	90	30
2	Lack of Sustainable Development	58	19.33
3	Destruction of Property	33	11
4	Deaths of Citizens	25	8.33
5	Displacement	20	6.67
6	Economic Losses	43	14.33
7	Migration	31	10.33
TOTAL		300	100

Source Field Report 2023.

Table 4 presents the opinions of the respondents on socio-economic consequences of insecurity in Ondo State. From the table, out of 300 respondents, 90(30%) respondents opined that insecurity caused poor industrial growth in Ondo State; 58(19.33%) agreed with the lack of sustainable development; 33(11%) agreed with destruction of both private and government property; 25(8.33%) opined that insecurity has led to loss of hundreds of lives of Ondo State indigenes; 20(6.67%) agreed with displacement of rural inhabitants from their homes; 43(14.33%) agreed with economic losses while 31(10.33%) opined that higher migration of people from rural to urban centres and from urban centres to neighbouring and overseas countries is a consequence of the prevailing insecurity in Ondo State. From the above analysis, it can therefore, be inferred that majority of the respondents are of opinion that insecurity is responsible for the poor industrial growth in Ondo State.

Research Question 4: How effective are the government's efforts in combating insecurity in Ondo State?

Table 5: Respondents' opinions on the effectiveness of governments' efforts in combating insecurity in Ondo State.

S/N	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Effective	82	27.33
2	Ineffective	218	72.67
Total		300	100

Source Field Report 2023

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 ISSN: 3043-6087. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Table 5 presents the opinions of the respondents on the effectiveness of governments' efforts in combating insecurity in Ondo State. From the table, out of 300 respondents, 82(27.33%) respondents agreed that government's efforts in combating insecurity in Ondo State are effective while 218 (72.67%) respondents are of the opinions that governments' efforts are not effective in combating insecurity in Ondo State

From the above analysis, majority of the respondents opined those efforts of the governments are not effective in combating the prevailing insecurity in Ondo state.

Discussion of Results

This study aims to appraise insecurity in Nigeria and its socio-economic consequences using Ondo State as a study. The results of the analyses of the research questions collated from 300 respondents revealed that the rate of insecurity is high in Ondo State. These findings corroborated the findings of Ndubuisi-Okolo and Anigbuogu (2019) who concluded that Nigeria is fraught with violent conflicts, chaos, anarchy, disorderliness, and retrogression as a result of the high level of unemployment and poverty among Nigerians especially youths who are adversely attracted to violent crimes, and the reports of Akingboye (2019, June 11), Akinkuotu (2019, July 11), Unity Party of Nigeria (2019, September 14) and Akinyemi (2020, August 11) in some Nigerian newspapers.

The position of the study that poor industrial growth has been a major consequence of the prevailing insecurity in the state was supported by Udeoba and Eze (2021) whose findings revealed that high level of insecurity discourages investments and can lead to outright closure of many enterprises especially in the areas where incidences of insecurity are common. The study also revealed that the existing governments' efforts in combating the criminal activities of the state are not effective. This finding was in agreement with the findings of Akingbade (2022) who posited that the conventional security architecture of Ondo State government has been grossly inadequate to combat the sophisticated trend of crime and terrorism in this 21st century and the findings of Edeko (2011) and Geographic Information System (GIS) Resources (2015) that asserted that previous measures to check mate the proliferation of small arms and light weapons by the government had not been effective. Hence, there should be an upgrade of security architecture for more proactive results.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of this study have shown that insecurity has been a major challenge to governments at all levels in Nigeria. The actions and good intentions of these governments have not been able to surmount the deleterious impact of the ravaging scourge. Hence, there is need for governments and international partners to reorder their conventional strategies and collaborate with civil populace in order to get better understanding of the root causes of insecurity in Nigeria with the aim of confronting the challenges of insecurity not only in Ondo State but Nigeria at large. The following recommendations are hereby needed in line with my observations, for the improvement of security in Ondo State.

- The government should provide jobs and empowerment for the teeming unemployed youths.
- The governments should improve measures that will enhance security at the borders.
- The Amotekun security network should be provided with modern equipment and gadgets and be well funded. The operations of the security corps should be backed with relevant laws.
- The Ondo state government should employ geospatial technology and other modern technologies like CCTV cameras to monitor crimes.
- Community policing should be well entrenched and the capability of the Nigeria police should be improved.
- The government should control the proliferation of small arms and light weapons.
- The weak criminal justice system should be strengthened. The present system contributes to the culture of impunity.
- Public awareness campaigns about security should be more vigorous among the general public and in schools.
- Governments should promote good governance, justice and fair distribution of political positions and wealth to reduce violent agitation for self -determination by various ethnic groups.

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